

Study from Usefulness of Digital Marketing Issues

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How to cite this paper: New Tin Tin Yu "Study from Usefulness of Digital Marketing Issues" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-5, August 2019, pp.1236-1239, <https://doi.org/10.31142/ijtsrd26625>

ABSTRACT

Digital marketing is continually evolving. New technologies enhance ability to collect information about customers. It is all about marketing on the internet and the other electronic devices. It's not a single process but it consists of a number of sub-components. Marketing has always been an important function of any business, and its overall impact on an organization is undeniable. This is a bit more amorphous and harder to understand in the beginning, businesses that are able to adapt quickly and adopt these methods are far more likely to see long-term success. Digital marketing is all online marketing efforts. It is promotion that takes place on the internet via different channels. Digital marketing really mention the concept of bringing what makes a company unique to the lead of devices customers are using. There is slight benefit to be established in a one-size-fits-all marketing approach. Digital marketing enables businesses to grab customer attention in a fast and convenient route by finding customers on their devices. Digital Marketing is a term defined to achieve business objectives and goals using the online channels.

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KEYWORDS: Traditional Marketing, Digital marketing, Digital marketing channels, Online marketing Channels, Offline Marketing Channels

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital marketing contains all marketing efforts that apply an electronic device or the internet. Businesses control digital channels such as search engines, social media, email, and other websites to attach with current and anticipated customers. Digital marketing is identified by the use of abundant digital devices and channels to associate with customers where they apply much of their time: online. From the website it to a business's online branding effects: digital advertising, email marketing, online brochures, and beyond: there's a spectrum of strategy that fall under of "digital marketing." The best digital marketers have a clear picture of how each digital marketing promotion supports their central goals. And depending on the goals of their marketing strategy, marketers can carry on a larger promotion through the free and funded channels at their disposal. Digital marketing is accomplished across many marketing roles today. In small companies, one generalist might own many of the digital marketing approach specified above at the same time. In larger companies, these approach have multiple specialists that each attention on just one or two of the brand's digital channels. The best digital marketers have a clear picture of how each digital marketing promotion supports their overarching goals. Digital marketers are in charge of driving brand appreciation and lead generation through all the digital channels: both free and paid that is at a company's action. These channels include of social media, the company's own website, search engine rankings, email, display advertising, and the company's blog.

2. Objectives

The objective of digital marketing is to accommodate online aspect to business through website and

social media. It can apply awareness about brand and help support to customer by handling their grievance and queries, which finally controls to sales, customer acquisition & satisfaction. Digital marketing has always been the liked many businesses and organizations, and it won't be abuse to say considering the current market situation, is a liked of all the businesses. Digital Marketing concludes many strategies of marketing for various promotional activities of businesses harnessing the best online platforms. The aim of digital marketing is to provide all the businesses to attract this increasing online population and thereby act the most of this digitalization process, by themselves shifting all their marketing activities online. Thus Digital Marketing was appeared using the digital platform. Digital marketing has given many organizations in order to provide them grow. And is still doing so by continually enhancing itself and its relevant strategies by keeping pace with the ever-changing technological scenario. Many search engines and social media specifies constantly keep changing their algorithms to provide make their interface and working easy to use for the increasing population using them. And so even digital marketing has been an evolving field and constantly developing in accordance with these changes.

3. Methodology

Digital marketing can work for any business in any industry. Regardless of what our company sells, digital marketing still involves building out buyer personas to identify our audience's needs, and creating valuable online content. However, that's not to say all businesses should implement a digital marketing strategy in the same way. A *digital marketing strategy is a detailed plan on how we can utilize the different digital marketing channels to achieve our*

business goals. When we design a digital marketing strategy we need to consider which channels to use, the resources (people, time and money) to assign to each channel and what to expect in terms of results. A common mistake made by many digital marketing managers or small business owners is that they try to execute everything at once and at the end of the day they get no results. Either because don't have the necessary expertise to run digital marketing promotions or because they end up spending their budgets on channels that is not suitable for their business. The main difference between digital marketing and traditional marketing is that digital marketing campaigns are executed exclusively through digital channels and this gives marketers more control, tools and data to analyze the effectiveness of a campaign. There are two types of marketing which have almost similar objectives:

Traditional Marketing - like billboards, banners, newspaper ads, flex posters etc.

Digital marketing - like SEO, SEM, SMM, Email marketing, content marketing, PPC, paid advertising and list might go on.

The nine main objectives of Digital marketing are:

- To create Brand Awareness
- To generate potential leads through advertising
- To increase engagement amongst the audience related to our domain or business.
- Reducing bounce rate on our website.
- Market segmentations on basis of our product.
- Increasing customer satisfaction and brand loyalty.
- Understanding our consumer's needs and connecting with them directly.
- Promote our new services or product launches.
- Surveys our audience to validate our product and its application in long run.

3.1 Digital marketing channels

Digital marketing has a number of channels and these can be separated into online marketing channels and offline marketing channels. The main difference between the two is that *online marketing channels* are based solely on the Internet while *offline marketing channels* have to do with digital devices which are not necessarily connected to the Internet.

3.1.1 Online marketing Channels

- Website Marketing
- Search Engine Optimization
- Pay-Per-Click Advertising
- Content Marketing
- Email Marketing
- Social Media Marketing
- Affiliate Marketing
- Inbound Marketing
- Mobile Marketing
- Video Marketing

A. Website Marketing

A website is the focal point of all digital marketing campaigns. By itself is a very powerful channel but it's also the medium to execute most of the other online marketing promotions. Our website should represent our brand, product and services in the best possible way. It should be fast, mobile friendly and easy to use. Once we have a website our next step is to come up with a digital marketing strategy and promote our website and content with the purpose of getting more traffic and customers.

B. Search Engine Optimization (SEO)

Search engine optimization is the process of optimizing our website for search engines. The main goal of SEO is to help a website rank higher in the search results and get organic (free) traffic from search engines. SEO has a number of sub-processes. The main ones are:

- Technical SEO
- On-Page SEO
- Off-Page SEO

C. Pay-Per-Click (PPC) Advertising

PPC advertising gives us the ability to reach internet users on a number of networks through paid ads. We can setup PPC campaigns on Google, Bing, LinkedIn, Twitter, Pinterest or Facebook and show our ads to people searching for terms related to our products or services. PPC campaigns can segment users based on their demographic characteristics (age, gender etc.) or even their particular interests or location. Every time a user clicks on our ads, we pay a fee to the provider (and thus the term *pay per click*). The most popular PPC platforms are Google Ads and Facebook. PPC Campaigns and SEO make up what is known as Search Engine Marketing (SEM).

D. Content Marketing

Content marketing is all about the content. The digital world is a huge collection of content in different forms like text, images, audio and video. The goal of a content marketing campaign is to reach potential customers through the use of content. Content is usually published on a website and then promoted through social media, email marketing, SEO or even PPC campaigns. The

difference between having a blog versus running a content marketing campaign is that the later has specific goals as to what content to publish, when to publish it, who to target, and how to monitor the effectiveness of our content campaigns. The main tools of content marketing are:

- Blogs
- eBooks
- Online Courses
- Info graphics
- Podcasts
- Webinars

E. Email Marketing

Despite the increase use of social media networks, email marketing is still one of the most effective digital marketing channels. Many people confuse email marketing with the hundreds of spam email messages we all receive per day, but that's not what email marketing is all about. Email marketing is the medium to get in touch with our potential customers or the people interested in our brand and this entails that these people want to hear from us and we are not hijacking their inbox. In fact, many successful online businesses and marketers use all other digital marketing channels to add leads to their email lists and then through email marketing they create a number of funnels to turn those leads into customers.

F. Social Media Marketing

Social media marketing has to do with reaching people in the various social networks either through content marketing promotions, paid ads or both. The primary goal of a social media marketing promotion is brand awareness and establishing social trust but as we go deeper into social media marketing, we can use it to get leads or even as a direct sales channel. Take for example Facebook. A Facebook sales funnel consists of 3 major steps. The top of the funnel is *awareness*: This is the stage where we can use Facebook ads to introduce our brand to Facebook users. Our goal at this stage is to get our ad in front of as many people as possible and gain new followers. The second step is *consideration*: At this stage our goal is to get people and pass them through the middle of the funnel and get them to visit our website, engage with our page, install our app, send us a message, etc. The third step is *conversion*: This is the final step where we try to convince people that enter our funnel to convert. A conversion can be anything that has value for our business like a sale of a product or service or a visit to our store.

G. Affiliate Marketing

Affiliate marketing is one of the oldest forms of marketing that has grown considerably with the rise of Internet usage. Basically, with affiliate marketing we promote other people's products and we get a commission every time we make a sale or introduce a lead. Many well-known companies like Amazon have affiliate programs that pay out millions of dollars per month to websites that sell their products. When designing our digital marketing strategy, we should include affiliate marketing as a way to get people involved in our brand and sell our products for a commission. In other words, when we have a product or service to promote online, we should consider setting up an affiliate program where people can sign up and find

resources and material they can use to promote our products on the Internet. They will get a commission as a reward but the benefits for us as a provider are much more. Our affiliates cannot only drive more sales but they can become the best representatives of our brand and positively influence other people to buy or connect with our company.

H. Inbound Marketing

Inbound marketing is another fancy term that refers to how we can use various digital marketing channels to reach new customers mainly through the process of content creation and how to 'push' them through a funnel until they convert. Inbound Marketing: Costs Per Lead. The main elements of inbound marketing are: content, attention, engagement, trust and satisfaction. All these elements have a single goal: to help businesses connect with their potential customers and establish a channel of by bi-directional communication with them that will lead to more sales. All digital marketing channels have similar sales funnels. What differs in many cases is the terminology used to describe each stage of the funnel. In general, a digital sales funnel has 3 main goals: to get people learn our brand, to get them engage with our brand (either through our website or app), and to get them to convert.

I. Mobile Marketing

Mobile marketing refers to the process of reaching customers in the different mobile app stores such as Google Play, Apple app store or Amazon marketplace. These app stores have thousands of apps and millions of users per day. With mobile marketing we can promote our apps either through paid advertising or through other methods (cross app promotions etc.), so that they can be seen and installed by more users. Making our website mobile friendly is a must and necessary otherwise our website won't show up for Google searches performed on mobile. Mobile marketing is about creating an app and uploading that app to Google Play or other app stores for users to download.

J. Video Marketing

Video marketing is something relatively new but recently it has become so popular that we simply cannot ignore it. YouTube has become the second most popular search engine and a lot of users are turning to YouTube before they make a buying decision, to learn something or just to relax. YouTube is just one of the mediums we can execute Video marketing. There are so many other platforms like Facebook Videos, Instagram, Vimeo to use to run a video marketing campaign. The best way to take advantage of video is to integrate them in your SEO, content marketing and social media marketing campaigns. Running standalone video campaigns can be costly and does not always create a positive return on investment, but when video is used as part of your other campaigns, the ROI is justified. We will examine below some examples on how to use Video marketing as part of a digital marketing strategy.

3.1.2 Offline Marketing Channels

The channels described above are the most important components of digital marketing. These are the channels that can be executed through the Internet (thus the

term *online marketing channels*) and in many cases; it's the only ones we need to use to have a strong online presence. The *offline digital marketing channels* described below are still used but they are not suitable for all companies. For example, a small business does not have the funds to advertise on TV or electronic billboards. Offline marketing channels are:

- TV Marketing
- SMS Marketing
- Radio Marketing
- Billboard Marketing

A. TV Marketing

TV marketing is not dead, on the contrary is a marketing channel that will experience a boost in the coming years. Currently TV advertising is not 100% targeted. Marketers can only make assumptions based on the statistics they have from a limited amount of people. The adoption of Web TV will change this dramatically. Marketers will be able to target audiences based on a number of factors and make informed decisions as to what content to produce.

B. SMS Marketing

SMS marketing is still an option to get in touch with potential customers, although not among the most powerful. There are better alternatives these days like push messages on the web and mobile and also on Facebook messenger. Nevertheless, SMS marketing can be used to get more visits to your local community store.

C. Radio Marketing

Radio marketing is another tool we can utilize but not so effective as other methods. The main issue with radio marketing is that we don't know exactly the return on our investment. When we pay for a radio ad, we can only assume on the amount of people that heard the ad, based on the number of listeners the particular radio station has. Radio marketing is still good for local businesses though and small communities that are not so affected by the social media mania.

D. Billboard Marketing

Billboard marketing is considered to be part of digital marketing. Electronic billboards are available in a number of public places (think Times Square billboards or Super Bowl commercials) and it's another more traditional channel in our digital marketing arsenal.

3.1.3 Benefits of Digital Marketing for organizations and businesses

- Digital marketing is well known for its cost-effectiveness since it uses all the cheaper means of promotions as opposed to the traditional means.
- It is more reliable and faster since it uses the online mediums.

- It helps fosters real-time interactions with the customers, providing them online instant feedback for any queries of theirs thereby gaining their trust.
- It helps with a wider outreach to a larger customer base with the help of digital media or to be more precise the social media, where many users have already logged in.
- Thus it helps organizations with increasing their revenues.
- It helps businesses with an increased ROI manifold.
- It uses all the latest technology trends and hence is always relevant and makes it easier for various industries and users to use it.
- It has also removed all the competitive barriers and thus brought everyone on a level playing field.

4. Conclusion

Many search engines and social media firms constantly keep changing their algorithms to help make their interface and working easy to use for the increasing population using them. And so even digital marketing has been an evolving field and constantly upgrading in accordance with these changes. That's the scoop on digital marketing. The internet is not the only place for marketers to gain success, even today. Of course, no one can give to miss out on the opportunities of the web and, eventually, every marketer will have to master online marketing. But, employing a little of these offline marketing approach can help us to not put all of our eggs into one basket and diversify our lead generation beyond social media, content marketing and the like.

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